

PLANET4B Project

understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making

Report on Workshop 1

Intensive case study: Opening up nature and the outdoors to Black, Asian and ethnic minority communities.

Sunday 4th February at Mercure Lambert Hotel in Oxfordshire UK

From CU: Alex Franklin (AF), Geraldine Brown (GB) and Lindy Binder (LB) [*Apologies: Barbara Smith (BS)]

From Dadima's CIC: Geeta (GL), Subash (SL), plus 7 people who have attended Dadima's walks.

Time	Item	Lead(s)
9am	Pre meeting for facilitators and Dadima's SL & GL Greet participants from 9.30am onwards (told to arrive for 9.45)	
10.00-10.15	Morning session welcome and introductions led by Dadima's. Explain/recap Dadima's vision – PLANET4B relationship – the what and why – Dadima's introduces AF, GB, BS* and LB to say a little on their roles (1 min each max), introduce structure of day briefly.	SL & GL
10.15	What is PLANET4B including welcome video from project's Principal Investigator, Ilkhom Soliev, providing the Learning Community with an overview of the project, the journey so far and the significance of their role (AF) Why are you here (what is a learning community)? (AF) Discussion around ethical considerations and consent (GB)	AF
10.30	Participant introductions via an image/object of something they find beautiful (all to participate; 2mins per person)	GB
11.00	An introduction to thinking about biodiversity in the Chilterns? (game)	LB
12.00	Lunch	GL/SL
12.45	System mapping exercise (pathways) – inner circle	AF & SL
13.45	Comfort break	
14.00	System mapping part 2 – outer circle. From the pathways exercise - how do we want to work going towards?	AF
14.50	Summary of journey, next meetings	AF, GB,
15.05	Close and thank you Postcard thoughts/words	GL/SL

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Introductions

We began by showing the group a [4-minute video](#) introduction to PLANET4B (P4B), recorded especially for the purpose, with project Principal Investigator, Ilkhom Soliev. The film was an opportunity for Ilkhom to personally welcome Learning Community Participants, provide an overview of P4B and an insight into the journey so far, as well as how the Learning Community (LC) feeds into the wider body of work.

The Learning Community comprises eleven individuals, from an ethnic minority community (predominantly South Asian people from Hindu, Sikh and Gujarati faith backgrounds) who have previously participated in walks organised by Dadima's CIC. Geeta and Subash are the leaders of the group and occupy a dual role as learning community participants and co-facilitators.

In the first workshop, seven of the eleven participants attended (nine of thirteen to include Geeta and Subash), this included six females and two males of South Asian descent (two of the females were born and spent some of their childhood living in Africa). One female participant identified as Black African heritage. Other demographics can be seen below:

Non-dependent children: over 16

Dependent children: under 16 or aged 16-18 and in full time education

Other multi-person household: flat shares, single parents with non-dependent children only, households containing more than one couple or single parent.

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GB led a discussion around **informed consent** both for being a research participant, by taking the group through the Participant Information Sheet, and around how images may potentially be used by P4B. All participants gave consent to be research participants. Five agreed to allow P4B to use photographs of their face. Two agreed to be in photographs provided they couldn't be identified.

Participants and researchers briefly introduced themselves via an object or picture of **something they find beautiful**. During the activity, the group shared stories about their artefact that were related to their personal relationships with nature and biodiversity. They talked about their love for gardening, collecting stones, foraging, pets, and how being in nature motivated them to capture its beauty through photography. This activity helped provide an initial insight into the Learning Community's connection with nature and biodiversity

LB led a biodiversity **game**, where a labelled picture of an organism was affixed to a band on the head of each player. They had to take turns to ask questions to the group that had 'yes' or 'no' answers (e.g. Am I a plant? Can I fly?) to enable them to guess the identity of the picture they had been assigned. This led into a more serious discussion around connection to nature and land.

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As each participant discovered their assigned plant or animal, they had varying reactions. The daisy and bluebell were seen as more desirable than the snail or frog. The owl sparked a debate as its symbolism differs in different cultures: while in British culture the owl is associated with wisdom, in Indian culture it was deemed by a member of the Learning Community as may be viewed as a negative comparison.

Participants pointed to superstitions of their parents and grandparents around animals often chosen as pets in the UK (e.g. cats). Public health messages such as ‘dogs are

outside’, ‘animals carry germs’ were referenced as perhaps underpinning some of these ‘superstitions’ as well as folklore and stories.

During the discussion the group referenced cultural traditions associated with the birth of a child: a baby girl is often/historically presented with messages of avors (meaning sympathy in Panjabi) while gender preference for a boy means that traditional Indian sweets called ladoos are distributed. One member describes her grandfather as being very progressive as he presented her with the Ladoo fifty years ago, despite her being a girl.

The group recognised that many ‘wise women’ or ‘medicine women’ (women intrinsically linked to nature) have historically been branded ‘witches’ with all the negative connotations this label has. One participant shared her recent positive engagement watching a Pagan ritual around winter solstice. The group recognised how many ‘pagan rituals’ are actually connected to agriculture.

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When you work really closely with the land, I think that you're really working with your intuition as well. And as we've moved on in these modern times, our intuition has really been eroded.

Talk turned to the history of the Chilterns area (the location for all/most of Dadima's walks). One participant shared that, there are a lot of Oak trees in the area left over from the era when oak was used for warships. As modern ships used other materials, demand went down but oak is still used in local building around the Chilterns (often stipulated by local authorities) and the manufacturers: Oak Furniture Land and Chiltern Oak continue to be based there.

What's fascinating about the conversation is how we have all these cultural variations but also how we're learning the history of this country as migrants and the relationship between not only our heritage but also our heritage or our migratory position here.

During the discussion, GB, who was a member of the research team, shared her experience of being of Caribbean heritage. She expressed how her understanding of lineage was impacted by the lack of information about her ancestry. Due to the gaps in history, she could only trace her heritage back to a certain point. Although DNA tracing provided some insight, the transatlantic slave trade had caused a loss of knowledge about her ancestry.

The majority of the group consisted of second-generation female migrants of South Asian descent, who shared similar and different experiences regarding the complexities surrounding aspects of their identity.

My family were born in Uganda and while our upbringing had been Ugandan-Gujarati-Indian English, it's choosing the best of everything to try to figure out who you want to be here.

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There was a long and rich discussion around connection to the land. One participant talks about how meditating with oils 'bypasses all the cognitive connections and goes straight to history, feeling and emotions' so it can help provide a connection to past and land particularly if a scent is chosen that may already have a connection to a place. Others talked about a grandparent bringing a small bag of soil from their country of origin or a drop of water from the River Ganges in preparation for their death, to connect them to their place of birth and in line with Hindu religious rituals. A discussion around death rituals and related creation stories in a variety of cultures and religions all appeared to bear a significant connection to land.

The discussion around death, grief and loss, led to a reflection on the term 'biodiversity loss', how the word loss has become synonymous with death – I'm sorry for your loss. The group also reflected on how some traditional death rituals (such as religious artefacts made from certain materials or chemicals) or paints and inks from particular festival celebrations may lead to the pollution of rivers in India, and thus contribute to biodiversity loss, even if historically these items were made from natural substances that shouldn't harm the environment, some modern iterations are not. Geeta shared the example of rakhis as part of Raksha Bandhan where they were often thrown in rivers. There are sustainable rakhis today.

System mapping

As part of the PLANET4B initiative, the Intensive Case Studies team is tasked with conducting a system mapping exercise within their learning communities.

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Mapping our connections to nature through Dadimas

The purpose of the exercise is to identify the key factors that influence the system (Dadima's) and to organise them based on their degree of influence. Additionally, the team may also identify key relationships between these factors, including both positive and negative relationships.

Led by AF, the participants were divided into three groups of three and tasked with exploring their views and experiences of Dadima's CIC and how they perceived the role it played within minoritised communities and more widely.

These results were fed back to the larger group and amalgamated into the **inside ring** of the systems map.

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It all came back to shared values and what is Dadima's. The shared value of the nature and the countryside, but actually people go there because it's a kind, safe environment for everybody to belong and to make new friendships... it is a very spiritual place – full of trust and acceptance.

Highlights included: community, shared values, sense of belonging, educational, wellbeing, diversity, environmental, cultural connection, social, intergenerational, physical health, mental health, safety, freedom, spirituality, connection to ancestors and story sharing.

Below the quotations give a flavour of the conversation:

We talked about ancestors in relation to some of the faith and religious dialogues we have on the walks, that maybe you can't always talk to people in the West – they may not appreciate them. There are some conversations I can have with Dadima's walkers where some of my friends at work might think I'm a bit mad...

The professionals that come, the lecturers – I love it! I love the knowledge that's there. It's great learning about the ecosystems, and the geology and the rock formations.

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There's a real sense of belonging coming to Dadima's. It's really been lovely to be included. Individuals in the group make you feel very welcome, and you have a sense of value, being there.

The second part of the System Mapping exercise involved participants returning to their groups of three, to consider the barriers and enablers to community-led initiatives such as Dadima's. Information generated was collected on sticky notes, and each group individually recorded responses on flipchart paper, which the Coventry University team collated and grouped thematically in the **outside ring** of the systems map.

Many of the factors identified could be both barriers and enablers, such as location or changes to life circumstances. Media promoting the outdoors and social media influencing environmental awareness were cited as enablers. The leaders of Dadima's were recognised as an enabler in terms of welcome, organisation and planning. This could be seen as a challenge if the group were to be replicated, as the administration can be a burden at times. Other factors noted included access to the countryside; including parking and associated costs, public transport networks, provision for elderly people or those with a disability – are there paths for wheelchair users? Are there toilet facilities?

While walks are seen as beneficial for physical and mental health, walk leaders shared that there were administrative challenges in planning the walks and the related admin.

Family events will take priority over our own self-care, our own wellbeing.

A distinction was drawn between first- and second-generation migrants:

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We're second generation. When our parents came, their purpose was to make life better, not only for us, for themselves, but all the people back home. So, there was no time for nature. They were time poor so therefore we did not have the exposure. We're time rich now.... Happiness is beginning to come into our psyche... to focus on other things rather than just creating wealth.

There was significant discussion around rural racism and the countryside as a 'white space': a perception of being unwelcomed, which manifested in not being greeted (always the person of colour greets first), or stereotyping "are you the Muslim Hikers from TV?" "We had one of you come and do samosas last time". Also discussed were the geographical nuances, walking in Bradford (where everybody greets everybody) compared to Watford (where nobody does). One participant didn't perceive non greeting as racialised, but rather interpreting it as choosing the peace and quiet and solitude of nature. What the Learning Community agreed, however, is that they like that Dadima's is an open group that does not exclude people:

Getting out and having a group that is not restricted to just white or black or brown or whatever is it is starting to break down stereotypes, whether that's stereotypes in terms of culture or whether that's stereotypes in terms of religion. Having groups that are open to everyone I think helps break down some of those barriers. I've certainly seen evidence of that on our walks.

For the final part of the systems mapping exercise, each participant was given three stars to stick to the sticky note factor they felt was most important to focus on as part of PLANET4B. They could choose to stick all three of their stars on just one factor or spread them out across two or three topics.

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Results as follows:

Factors associated with the delivery of community initiatives like Dadima's	Barrier/ Enabler	Number of stars
Media promoting the outdoors	Enabler	4
Changing lifestyles	Enabler	2
Organisation involved in planning walks; routes	Barrier	2
The potential for racism if the group got too big	Barrier	2
Distance and cost of travel	Barrier	1
Fear of the unknown, phobias (eg. fear of snakes in nature)	Barrier	1
GDP is happiness	Enabler	1
Generational teaching habits	Enabler	1
Money needed for good clothing/ cost of leisure	Barrier	1
Not only black and brown, but inclusive of white people	Enabler	1
Social media influencing environmental awareness	Enabler	1
Time and distance – impact on environment	Barrier	1

Participants also selected some of the factors from the central ring:

The role Dadima's plays within ethnic minority communities	Number of stars
Sharing stories	2
Education and knowledge	2
Learning experience	1
Intergenerational	1
Open to all	1
Free therapy	1

After the workshop, we created a digital version of the systems map grouping similar themes by placement and colour of sticky-note.

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Wrap up and next steps

Seven of the eleven participants selected for the learning community were in attendance. The other four will be contacted via a shorter online meeting to be brought up to speed.

GB will conduct 30-minute interviews online with each participant to begin exploring the research questions with each member individually.

GL set up a Learning Community WhatsApp group with all participants and researchers to share photographs, stories and relevant articles to offer connection, enthusiasm and vigour for the project between workshops. This is already being well used with photos of participants out in nature and nature/ biodiversity related article links.

The day concluded with postcards of hopes – participants could write one thing they hoped to do between this first and the second workshop (scheduled for April 2024) to engage with biodiversity in some way.

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Early indications from the systems mapping show this Learning Community believes communication is an important enabler in facilitating the engagement of ethnic minority communities in nature and biodiversity. GB shared a participatory film developed by Walking Warriors, a local walking group of people from an African Caribbean Heritage. The Learning Community were supportive of the idea to explore participatory filmmaking for themselves so we will pick this up at a future workshop.